

TRADITIONS IN FARMING AND GARDENING AND THEIR MODERNIZATION

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Abstract

In this article, while observing the views and ceremonies related to the traditional lifestyle of the Uzbek people, we can see that the special respect for land, grain and bread is still preserved in various customs and ceremonies.

Key words: agriculture, horticulture, rituals, human nature, fertility, tradition, ethnographic;

INTRODUCTION

It is known from history that farming and horticultural traditions were an important factor in the emergence and development of ancient centers of human civilization. The formation and development of horticultural culture in the East, which is one of the ancient centers of world civilization, is distinguished by the fact that it is based on irrigation farming. In this regard, it is worth saying that the oldest farming culture in Central Asia is the Joytun culture, which indicates that it was formed in 6-4 thousand years BC.

MAIN PART

The study of the history of agriculture and horticulture is very important in the scientific analysis of the socio-economic system of peoples and the development of production forces and the problems of the history of economic and cultural types at different stages of history. Since ancient times, farming and horticultural culture, traditional farming and related rituals and agrarian cults have always been one of the most relevant and interesting problems for historians, archaeologists and ethnologists. as a result, certain practical results were also achieved.

Especially in this regard, the history of horticulture and farming culture in the territory of Uzbekistan, the stages of formation and development of irrigated agriculture, and the urban processes related to it are always considered as urgent problems. In researching the history of the oldest agricultural culture, horticultural rituals and their genesis in the territory of our country, studying the

lifestyle of our ancestors, reconstructing historical processes, and studying the ancient state traditions of our people and ancient urbanistic processes in the region in a scientific way. is important.

In this regard, the world science has accumulated rich experience, and the German folklorist W. Mannhard first put forward the problem of revealing the secrets of the revitalization of the plant world in various myths and images with agriculture. According to W. Mannhardt, rituals embody the view that man lives in plants like all other creatures in nature.

In fact, farming traditions are connected to ancient roots and have their own rituals. The work process that is repeated at exactly the same time in each farming season has caused the formation of various traditions and customs.

Below, we will try to analyze the first images and customs of farming culture in our region on the basis of written sources, including the information of the sacred book of Zoroastrians "Avesta" and show their harmony with the traditional farming rituals of the Uzbek people.

It is known that in "Avesta" views on the rules of social order and various rituals related to the culture of early agriculture and horticulture are given a wide place.

The good aspects of farming are embodied in the image of Arvatatnara, Zarathustra's second child. Its characteristics include obedience to law and social order, and patience. Also, Arvatatnara is the first farmer in the world, according to the imagination of Mazda fans. According to "Vendidod" chapter 2, paragraph 42, Zarathustra and Arvatatnara are the greatest and wisest among the var people created by Yimakshayati (Jamshid). It is written in "Bundakhishn": "Arvatatnara was the greatest of the peasants, now he has become the greatest of the var built by Jamshid. It is worth mentioning here that according to the Zoroastrian tradition, Arvatatnara was among the eternal breeds.

In many places of the Avesta, one of the main factors in increasing productivity is advised to remove dirt from the land and wash it. In order to create an integrated agro-culture, Zoroastrians used a special irrigation system and an orderly distribution of land areas among the members of the community. It should be noted that among the types of punishments given to people for crimes, there was also a measure of forced use in the construction of water structures (this was considered hard physical labor). In this period, although land was communal property, livestock was private property. "we can expect from

In "Avesta" peasants are called "vastriofishuyant". If we look at the etymology of this word, we will witness a very interesting scene related to the traditional nomadic occupation of Zoroastrian ancestors - cattle breeding. According to A. O. Makovelskyi, an Avestologist, the phrase "vastriofishuyant" is a complex word, its first component means a cattle herder with big horns, and the second part means a cattle herder with small horns. After joining these two words, the word "farmer" appeared.

In the world view of our people and the traditional economic activity related to agriculture, some views related to these views have been preserved until now, and this is confirmed by direct ethnographic data. For example, among Uzbeks, plowing the land, preparing it for planting, fetching water, harvesting the crops grown on the ground is merit, farming is considered the most honorable occupation. In particular, the beginning of the farming season was celebrated in a special way, until the first quarter of the 20th century, in many regions of our republic, the ceremony of "discharge" was held before the spring plowing. In every family, women cooked steamed chozma ("is"). The oil is well heated in the cauldron, and then the dough is added to it. It is said that when the deceased hears the heat of this oil, their spirits are happy and they wish good luck to their relatives. Before plowing the land, the oxen's horns and yoke were greased with oil.

Amulets are worn to protect oxen from the evil eye. According to the elders, the intention is embodied in this tradition that the ox, whose horns are lubricated and strong, will work tirelessly throughout the year.

CONCLUSION

In short, the farming traditions of the Uzbek people have an ancient history, 3,000 years ago, farming flourished in the land of Central Asia and was one of the main occupations of the ancestors. The traditions and ceremonies related to farming and horticulture, the greatest profession described and promoted in "Avesta", are particularly noteworthy for their vitality and folkiness. There are no signs of social class limitations in them, they appeared on the ground of natural needs and served the interests of the whole nation. These traditions and ceremonies are dedicated to the work process and important life events related to nature and express the hopes and dreams of the people.

References:

1. Boriyev H. "Guide for amateur gardener". - Stone town. "Sharq" NMAK. - 2002, [p. 208]
2. Mirzayev M.M., Sobirov M.K. "Horticulture and viticulture". - Tashkent, Teacher. - 1975, [page 190.]
3. Fruit growing. - T.; Text of lectures. - [1993.p.]
4. Ribakov A.A., Ostrouxova S.A. "Uzbekistan Fruit Industry". - Tashkent, "Teacher". - 1981, [page 508]
5. State Register of agricultural crops recommended for planting in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2005. [Page 89]
6. Mahmudov M. A methodical manual for conducting laboratory exercises in the subject "With the basics of scientific research in agriculture". Against, 2010. [Page 92.]
7. Mominov K.M., Islamov I.S., Rizayev Sh.Kh. Methodical guide for conducting laboratory and practical training in agricultural science. - Samarkand, 2008. [Page 123.]
8. Mominov K., Azimbeyev S., Sanakulov A., Berdibayev E., Kenzhayev Yu. Agriculture with the basics of scientific research (Study guide). - T.: "Turon-Iqbal", 2014. [Page 69]
9. Sulaimanov I.S., Mominov K.M. Methodical guide to agriculture. - Samarkand, 1989. [Page 234];